

Plagiaruedo

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Keywords

Criminology, Critical Thinking, Educational Ethics, Humanities, International Relations, Learning Development, Politics, Social Sciences, Sociology

Figure 1. Conceptual image illustrating the theme of plagiarism detection and academic integrity addressed in *Plagiaruedo* (Laura Barclay, Ian Johnson). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

The game of *Plagiaruedo* is an adaptation of the European "Cluedo", or the game "Clue" in North America (see Figure 1). The main objective is to determine the culprit, the form of academic misconduct, and the reason for this choice. *Plagiaruedo* would be best used in introductory courses at post-secondary institutions. The game is intended as a conversation starter about academic integrity and potential misconduct, rather than to provide complete information about these concepts. When used as an introductory activity, students can become more engaged and informed about misconduct issues without feeling "threatened" by the topic. The designers have also included events in the game to speed up and vary gameplay, thereby affording greater interactivity. The game was developed by Laura Barclay and Ian Johnson of the University of Portsmouth in 2023–2024.

Facts

Release date: 2023
Developer: Laura Barclay, Ian Johnson

Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	3–6 (optimal with 3–4 for time)
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	30–45 minutes
Languages:	English
Environment:	–
Material:	May become print-and-play
Price:	Currently not publicly available; the makers plan to produce a second edition soon.

Resonance & Criticism

The game has been play-tested with instructors in the UK and Canada, and with students in the UK. Generally, it has been well received by all groups as a conversation starter to prompt metacognition and deeper engagement with integrity and misconduct concepts. A release of the game is in preparation.

The most challenging aspect, according to students and instructors, is the time required to play the entire game. At present, the game takes approximately 30–45 minutes, which can be a challenge to incorporate into a 50-minute university class.

Game principle & Process

Plagiaruedo is a mystery game modeled after the board game Cluedo (Clue in North America), where players use logical deduction to determine which cards are not held by other players. Plagiaruedo alters the theme to focus on academic misconduct rather than murder.

A set of cards (one suspect, one misconduct, and one rationale) is secretly removed before play and placed in an envelope on the board. Each player starts with a card hand that provides limited information and acquires more through dice-driven movement around the board and by asking targeted questions of other players to eliminate possibilities. Each player attempts to determine the identity of the hidden set of cards at the start of the game by strategically removing cards from other players' hands.

There is limited social interaction beyond gameplay, as the game is intended as a conversation starter and an initial activity to promote thought and discussion. It is a soft introduction to challenging concepts. The designers recommend a follow-up session to discuss aspects of the game. There are options to play competitively or collaboratively in teams or as a single group.

The scientific theory for the game is that challenging ideas may be more easily approached through a lens of play than through direct means (Mardell et al., 2023).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Plagiaruedo is designed to introduce students to the concepts of academic integrity, potential misconduct, and how misconduct can occur. This has led to an open discussion of the possible

consequences of these actions during playtesting. By introducing these ideas through a game, students tend not to feel "lectured at" and approach the concepts with a more critical lens, seeking meaning. Follow-up activities by the instructor can involve more probing questions that seek answers to prompts such as: "Where could a student find assistance for this challenge before resorting to this form of misconduct?"; "Given the forms of academic misconduct in the game, how would you rank them in order of severity?"; "What consequences do you think should accompany these issues?" As such, the instructor's role is largely facilitation during and after gameplay.

Effectiveness

Formal research is still underway. Initial play-testing and feedback sessions with instructors and students have been largely positive, with the game challenging conceptions about academic integrity and the use of games to introduce challenging topics into class.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The most significant challenge in implementation at present is the time required to introduce, play, and adequately debrief the game. While this time is valuable, instructors often feel that the information can be delivered more quickly through a lecture. Another challenge, which is currently being approached humorously, is adapting a game board that is "intentionally similar" to the actual Cluedo board. There is currently no intention to publish this commercially in this form. Hence, the use of recognizable copyrighted material in a game about plagiarism and academic misconduct adds a layer of context to the broader conversation.

This game is likely most appropriate for students who are relatively new to the structures, pressures, and requirements of the post-secondary environment.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Johannes Katsarov

Sources

Johnson, I., & Barclay, L. (2024). Plagiaruedo*: Teaching of academic integrity through a “whodunnit” game (*any likeness to other games is intentional!*). *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education*, (32). <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi32.1415>

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